
RIGHT TO EDUCATION ACT, 2009

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ABSTRACT

The Right to Education Act of 2009, also known as the RTE Act 2009, stands as a pivotal legislation for the welfare of children. Enacted by the Parliament on 4th August 2009, this Act underscores the importance of education, establishing it as a fundamental and compulsory right for children between the ages of 6 and 14. Free education is not just encouraged but mandated, recognized as a fundamental right under Article 21A of the Indian Constitution of 1949. However, despite its noble objectives, certain issues have emerged in the implementation of this Act, revealing shortcomings in both its policies and regulations. Some areas fall short in fulfilling the Act's intended purpose, pointing to a need for more effective execution. Additionally, inherent problems within the Act itself contribute to these challenges. While the RTE Act contains numerous rules and policies, there remains a gap between its intended goals and the actual outcomes. This gap calls for attention from both the government and the Parliament, urging them to address these issues, make necessary amendments, and ensure that the Act achieves its envisioned impact on the education landscape in India.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2009 Parliament came up with an act called Right to Education 2009 also known as RTE Act 2009, which describes that education is compulsory and free for the age between 6-14 years of child. It is also mentioned in the Indian Constitution under Article 21A which is a fundamental right means the Right to education is a fundamental right and it is inserted in the Eighty-Sixth Amendment in such a manner as the State may by rules and law, determine.

A Child has the Right to get free and full-time elementary Education which should be contentment and Delighted in Nature. Let's talk about when this Act came into force. This act came into force on 1st April 2010. Right to Education contains a total of 38 Sections and 7

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chapters. Now from 1st April 2010. This act comes into force and is applied in each state and also it is notified by the state government as well. In this Act, it is mentioned that Free and Compulsory Education. Hence, there is an Obligation on the government to ensure that the education which is provided in schools should be a Well quality education it should be quality not quantity. It should be free and every child (6-14) should be educated and taught by qualified teachers. Here there is a word called Free means No child shall be liable to pay any kind of fees, charges, and any expenses that might create issues or prevent them from getting a complete education. Section 2 of Right to Education defines words and expressions used in this act, it states that - provides to every child of the age of six to fourteen years the right to free and compulsory education in a neighbourhood school till the completion of elementary education. The idea of neighbourhood schools can be traced to the National System of Education as elaborated in the Kothari Commission report, whereby the neighbourhood school is meant to be a common space, where all children cutting across caste, class, and gender lines learn together in the best inclusive manner. It is therefore meant to be a site for inclusion so that the school becomes a common space for education. This concept has been incorporated into the RTE Act.

II. NEED OF THE STUDY

The author Studied this act so that people, governments and lawmaking bodies should aware that what are the major changes that need to be made and what are the problems that create barriers between children and education. The purpose of studying this act is to remove loopholes and major issues faced by children in past and present times as well. So that In Future no problem will be faced by any children and the Right to education will run smoothly without any intervention, yes, some laws need to be interpreted and changed.

III. PROBLEMS AND MAIN ISSUES

1. AGE GAP - Why limit free education to children aged 6-14? What options do children have after turning 14 if they cannot afford school fees and expenses? It is suggested that the age gap should be extended, ensuring completion of at least basic schooling.
2. QUALIFIED TEACHERS - In India, the issue of unqualified teachers persists. Instances have been reported where teachers lack proper qualifications and seriousness

about education. This matter should be addressed by the government, as highlighted cases in Bihar indicate a lack of basic knowledge among some teachers.

3. DETERMINATION TO PROVIDE QUALITY EDUCATION - The government needs to evaluate the dedication of teachers in government schools. Strict measures, including suspensions for irresponsible and inactive teachers, should be implemented. Additionally, there should be strict enforcement of laws and punishments for any violations.
4. EDUCATION AWARENESS - A significant portion of the population, particularly in rural and slum areas, lacks knowledge about legal rights. Legal awareness campaigns should focus on educating people about their rights, including the Right to Free Education and other fundamental rights and duties.
5. EDUCATION FREE ONLY UP TO CLASS 8 - Under the RTE Act of 2009, education is free for children aged 6-14, up to class 8. This provision should be reconsidered, and amendments should be made to extend free education beyond class 8 to ensure a more comprehensive educational journey.
6. FAULT/MENTALITY OF PARENTS - Some parents discourage their children from pursuing education, pushing them into child labour. Initiatives should be taken to prevent this, and parents should be encouraged to support their children's education for a brighter future.
7. DELAY IN DECLARING RESULTS - Result delays are often due to problems in time management. Efficient coordination and proper work processes within the education system can ensure that results are declared within the stipulated time.
8. LACK OF FOCUS ON SKILL-BASED EDUCATION - Teachers often prioritize exam marks over imparting practical knowledge. The education system should shift its focus to provide both theoretical and practical knowledge to address the skill gap.

9. NO CHANGE IN OLD EDUCATION SYSTEM - Despite the introduction of smartboards, their utilization is not as efficient as it should be. Efforts should be made to maximize the benefits of technological advancements in education.
10. CHEATING DURING EXAMS - Cheating remains prevalent in both private and government schools. Addressing this issue is crucial to ensure fair examinations and prevent students from resorting to dishonest practices.
11. QUESTION PAPER LEAK ISSUES - Instances of question paper leaks, not only in school exams but also in competitive exams, indicate negligence and security lapses. Measures should be taken to enhance the security of exam proceedings to prevent such incidents and ensure a fair examination environment.

Now what are the major causes of Child Labor in India?

- 1- Poverty
- 2- Gender Disparities
- 3- Demand for cheap labour
- 4- Economic Pressures on families
- 5- Lack of quality of Education

Parents should be aware their child that why education is necessary for their lives, and what the importance of education in life, they should not send their children to labour work or other activities that are prohibited by law.

There are two types of education formal and informal education, formal education is provided by the school itself, and rest is informal education which parents and teachers can teach them how, both education are important in the life of a child

IV. STATISTICS ON THE STATUS OF CHILD EDUCATION IN INDIA

The literacy ratio of India is 65.38% with male literacy at 75.85% and female literacy at 54.16%, Of the 193 million Children in the age group 6 to 14 years, 8.1 million children are out of school as of Sept 2004 as per Government statistics. Net primary enrolment ratio in 2001/02: 83 7%. Children reaching grade 5 in 2000/01: 59 8 %

V. MINISTRY OF FINANCE / PRESS INFORMATION BUREAU DATA-

Number of Primary Schools in India: 0.664 million (2001-02)
Number of Upper Primary Schools in India: 0.219 million
Population in the age group of 6-14 years: 193 million
Secondary and Senior Secondary Schools: 0.133 million; Enrollment: 30.5 million
Findings from the Survey: Social infrastructure like education is as important as physical infrastructure, not only for sustaining high growth but also for enhancing welfare. The root of poverty often lies in illiteracy.

VI. CENSUS OF INDIA 1991

- State with highest literacy rate: Kerala (89.8)
- State with lowest literacy rate: Bihar (38.5)
- District with the highest literacy rate: Kottayam, Kerala (95.7)
- District with lowest literacy rate: Jhabua, Madhya Pradesh (19.0)

VII. FACTS ON EDUCATION

- Less than half of India's children between the ages of 6 and 14 go to school.
- A little over one-third of all children who enrol in grade one reach grade eight.
- At least 35 million children aged 6 – 14 years do not attend school.
- 53% of girls in the age group of 5 to 9 years are illiterate.
- In India, only 53% of habitation has a primary school.
- In India, only 20% of habitation has a secondary school.
- On average an upper primary school is 3 km away in 22% of areas under habitation.
- In nearly 60% of schools, there are less than two teachers to teach Classes I to V.

- On average, there are less than three teachers per primary school. They have to manage classes from I to V every day.
- The high cost of private education and need to work to support their families and the lack of interest in studies are the reasons given by 3 in every four drop-outs as the reason they leave.
- Dropout rates increase alarming RESEARCH in class III to V, its 50% for boys, 58% for girls.
- 1 in 40, primary schools in India are conducted in open spaces or tents.
- In Andhra Pradesh (South India), 52 upper primary schools were operating without a building in 2002, while in 1993, there were none.
- In Maharashtra (West India), 10 schools were operating without a building in 1993, this has climbed to 33 in 2002.
- More than 50 per cent of girls fail to enrol in school; those that do are likely to drop out by the age of 12.
- 50% of Indian children aged 6-18 do not go to school

These facts clearly state that still our education system somewhere lacking and it should be fixed and changed as soon as possible for the betterment of child for their future and the betterment of society and the nation as well.

VIII. NOW WHAT ARE THE STEPS THAT SHOULD BE TAKEN TO IMPROVE THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

1. **QUALITY OF EDUCATION, NOT QUANTITY** - In India, we need to focus on the quality of education rather than quantity. The quality should be tailored according to the class, ensuring precision and understandability.

2. **TEACHERS SHOULD BE WELL-QUALIFIED** – Teachers should possess strong qualifications and experience, aligning with the classes they teach. The shortage of qualified teachers and their professional development is a significant shortcoming that requires immediate attention in our country. To achieve high-end educational goals and bridge existing gaps, expert educators are needed to translate theories into real classroom practices.
3. **RURAL EDUCATION IS IMPORTANT** – In India, rural education holds great significance. Often, rural education faces challenges such as shortages of books, teachers, smart classes, location disadvantages, school uniform issues, and more. Therefore, the primary focus should be on improving education in rural areas, as they lag compared to urban areas.
4. **PARENTS SHOULD BE EDUCATED OR EDUCATE PARENTS** – Parents should educate themselves and their children. In many rural areas, parents are often illiterate and unaware of the importance of education. Creating awareness about the significance of education is crucial.
5. **SUPPORT NGOS** – Supporting NGOs is essential, as they are non-profit organizations working for society and promoting social justice, playing a vital role in the education system as well.
6. **SMART CLASSES** – While smart classes can significantly enhance our education system, their efficient use is crucial. It's positive to see smart classes being implemented in many rural areas, but their potential should be fully utilized to deliver quality education.
7. **SET UP LIBRARIES** – The focus should be on establishing libraries. Building libraries with minimal fees will provide children with a comfortable study place without disturbances and contribute to the improvement of their skills and results.
8. **COMMAND ON COMPUTER (BASIC SKILLS)** – Schools should include computer education in their syllabus for the child's future development. Proficiency in computer skills enables students to solve problems efficiently and aids them in achieving their goals.

9. INVESTMENT – The government should make substantial investments in education to build and maintain infrastructure and support children who cannot afford education.
10. AWARENESS AND COUNSELING – Awareness and counselling are crucial for a child's mental well-being. These assessments help determine if a child is mentally fit, identify barriers such as parental, teacher, or personal issues, and prevent any steps that may negatively impact their life.

IX. CONCLUSION

The overall conclusion of this research paper emphasizes the need to improve education. The author aims to address various issues and implement necessary changes for the bright future of children and the growth of our education system. Education, being crucial for individuals, our nation, and every sector, requires attention. Without education, nothing substantial can be achieved. The author acknowledges the government's efforts in constructing buildings, developing infrastructure, focusing on child development, allocating funds to the education system, enhancing transportation, and implementing schemes that facilitate affordable education.

The government's provision of scholarships is also recognized as a significant support system for students. Scholarships play a vital role in addressing financial challenges and are beneficial for those students who genuinely aspire to pursue education. Despite the ongoing growth of the education system and the increasing number of students, the author suggests the necessity to expand seating capacity and ensure the timely availability of vacancies.

The author firmly believes that India, as a nation, will progress at an accelerated pace if these improvements are implemented. This, in turn, will contribute to the development of every sector in the country.

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